

Short Report

NTB-iron (NTBI): new insights in its effect on heart disease, dyslipidemia, and fatty liver in patients with hemochromatosis and H63D syndrome

Carolina Diamandis, David Seideman, Marianne Kaufmann

Corresponding Author

LCG Research
Dr. Marianne Kaufmann
Team of Dr. Seideman
16 Kifissias Avenue
115 26 Athens, Hellenic Republic
www.your-doctor.com

Abstract

The dangers caused by iron not bound to transferrin (NTBI) have been known for many years, however, they are not yet considered with adequate seriousness by the medical community as a cause of complex syndromes and a severe danger for patients with hemochromatosis, H63D syndrome and other conditions which lead to transferrin saturation >50%. This brief report informs about the deleterious effects of NTBI on the pituitary, lipid metabolism, heart structure and function as well as on damages to the liver.

The impact of NTBI on organ systems and homeostasis

The serious toxic damage NTBI iron causes to virtually all organ systems and parenchymal tissues is already well described in the literature. In particular, damage to the brain and male gonads have now become part of general medical knowledge. Because of the hazardous nature of NTBI-induced cardiac diseases and disorders of lipid metabolism, it should first be recalled which organs are particularly vulnerable to NTBI-induced toxic and inflammatory reactions.^{1,2,3,4,9,10} (Fig. 1)

Organs affected by NTBI iron poisoning

Fig.1

Heart

Cardiac damage is almost inevitable when NTBI accumulates. In most cases, a gradual NTBI accumulation takes place which can affect various structures of the heart via oxidative and inflammatory effects. In addition, chronically elevated levels of epinephrine can be detrimental to the heart, as NTBI can also affect adrenal function. Thus, several factors often interact in chronic NTBI poisoning. Since there is (still) no simple test for NTBI, this form of iron is rarely thought of when a younger person suddenly develops a heart condition or even structural heart damages. However, ignoring NTBI accumulation can quickly lead to far-reaching investigations that would not be necessary if the possibility of NTBI-induced heart damage were also considered. A clarification to this effect is neither complicated nor expensive, one just has to know what to look for.^{2,4,9,10}

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD)

NTBI accumulation can adversely alter fat metabolism in multiple ways, leading to fat accumulation in the liver (fatty liver/NAFLD) especially through LDL, VLDL and triglycerides. On the one hand, by a direct pathway through constant oxidative damage in hepatocytes, and on the other hand, by NTBI-induced dysfunction of the pituitary, adrenal, and thyroid glands. Since these are relatively subtle changes, they are not detectable with the capabilities of a standard laboratory. This can only be done in one of the few highly specialized centers of excellence to which practically no patient is ever referred. As a rule, these institutions are also inaccessibly far away or carry out corresponding examinations only within the framework of studies instead of offering established treatments. What can be considered certain, however, is that nutrition is only one factor among many that causes NAFLD in these cases. It is a complex interaction of various factors on which NTBI iron has a significant influence. The only universal advice that applies to all patients is to avoid alcohol consumption in general. All other advice can only be given on a case-by-case basis, if at all, in the case of accumulation of NTBI.^{3,7,8,9,10}

Lipid metabolism

Cholesterol synthesis as well as transport and administration of triglycerides can also be affected increasingly markedly over time in the case of irreversible NTBI overload/chronic poisoning. Here, too, the pituitary and thyroid glands play a role as important as the direct influence of NTBI on hepatocytes. In addition, an adrenal gland stressed by NTBI can additionally influence fat metabolism via excessive catecholamine production. A similar role applies to the pancreas, although the specific clinical consequences of NTBI overload of the pituitary, pancreas, and adrenal glands require further research. Data on clinical relevance is scant, and there is no motivation to invest in such studies. To this day, virtually every patient is sent home with the standard explanations for the development of NAFLD and other disorders of lipid metabolism, no matter how poorly they fit the specific case. Behavioral recommendations are made and sometimes medications are prescribed. The problem is, however, that >90% of these recommendations only deal with the topic of nutrition and metabolic syndrome and are thus simply useless for patients with NTBI overload. Especially "healthy" food is usually rich in iron. Thus, in many cases, a wrong treatment already starts at this point.¹⁻⁵

Conclusion

Until further well-established findings are available, in addition to a low-iron diet, patients should try to keep adrenaline levels as low as possible and engage in heart-friendly light daily exercise. Patients should be educated to pay very close attention to the iron content of their food, even if there is social pressure to try whichever 'healthy' diet or diets. Even foods as innocuous-seeming as vegan meat substitutes can contain extremely high amounts of iron by means of soy protein and wheat protein concentrates. Healthy eating is to be defined differently for a person overloaded with NTBI iron than for patients with an intact iron metabolism.

Conflicts of interest

none

References

1. Francesca Vinchi. Antioxidants & Redox Signaling. Aug 2021.387-414. <http://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2020.8167>
2. Sugiura, Tomonori et al. (2021) Analytical evaluation of serum non–transferrin-bound iron and its relationships with oxidative stress and cardiac load in the general population, *Medicine*: February 19, 2021 Volume 100 - Issue 7 - p e24722 doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000024722
3. Milic S, Mikolasevic I, Orlic L, Devcic E, Starcevic-Cizmarevic N, Stimac D, Kapovic M, Ristic S. The Role of Iron and Iron Overload in Chronic Liver Disease. *Med Sci Monit.* 2016 Jun 22;22:2144-51. doi: 10.12659/msm.896494. PMID: 27332079; PMCID: PMC4922827.
4. Patel M, Ramavataram DV. Non-transferrin bound iron: nature, manifestations and analytical approaches for estimation. *Indian J Clin Biochem.* 2012 Oct;27(4):322-32. doi: 10.1007/s12291-012-0250-7. Epub 2012 Aug 31. PMID: 24082455; PMCID: PMC3477448.
5. Ana-Maria Singeap, Carol Stanciu, Laura Huiban, Cristina Maria Muzica, Tudor Cuciureanu, Irina Girleanu, Stefan Chiriac, Sebastian Zenovia, Robert Nastasa, Catalin Sfarti, Camelia Cojocariu, Anca Trifan, Association between Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease and Endocrinopathies: Clinical Implications, *Canadian Journal of Gastroenterology and Hepatology*, vol. 2021, Article ID 6678142, 8 pages, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6678142>
6. Boshuizen M, van der Ploeg K, von Bonsdorff L, Biemond BJ, Zeerleder SS, van Bruggen R, Juffermans NP. Therapeutic use of transferrin to modulate anemia and conditions of iron toxicity. *Blood Rev.* 2017 Nov;31(6):400-405. doi: 10.1016/j.blre.2017.07.005. Epub 2017 Jul 24. PMID: 28755795.
7. Ponka P. Rare causes of hereditary iron overload. *Semin Hematol.* 2002 Oct;39(4):249-62. doi: 10.1053/shem.2002.35638. PMID: 12382200.
8. Anderson, G.J. 1999 Non-transferrin-bound iron and cellular toxicity. *Journal of Gastroenterology and Hepatology*, 14, 105–108.
9. Carolina Diamandis, Jacob S Adams, Riku Honda, et al. H63D Syndrome: What we know about it in 2021. *Authorea*. May 25, 2021. doi: 10.22541/au.162191694.46218714/v1

10. Carolina Diamandis, David Seideman, Smith Lucas. H63D: The Other Mutation (2021 version). Authorea. November 29, 2021. doi: 10.22541/au.163820567.76952749/v1Dr. Carolina Diamandis, William Smith, Marianne Kaufmann, et al. H63D-Syndrome: Quick Reference Guide . *Authorea*. December 16, 2021. doi: 10.22541/au.163967137.78856688/v1

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